

ACCESSING OPEN DATA ON NFT

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As social media has played an essential role in expressing individual ideas, connecting, communicating, and interacting with one another on the digital platform, it has also provided a novel set of data to understand our daily life (Kakulapati, 2021). Non-fungible token (NFT) is an extension of digital token transactions that emerged in 2021. It has also inherited a much more advanced set of data and provides an alternative for information and data communication. As NFT differs from fungible tokens, it is the presentation of the digital and unique transactions of tokens. Based on the blockchain system, NFT is intrinsically the demonstration of decentralised system applied in the transaction of digital work. Each property can be traded freely with the customized value that is set by the NFT creator (Wang et al., 2021). As the value is being set and generated through the smart contract, here the smart contract refers to the adapted contracts that are run by programs that are originally set by individuals, this means that every NFT transaction has complete freedom of setting its own contract conditions, with external interference. NFT transaction is also a transparent process (Wang et al., 2021). While the NFT transaction has been finished, there is a smart contract that has been generated through machines automatically and it is not reversible or editable. The whole transaction process and related information are all documented fully by the machine. Due to the existing transparent framework and the decentralised system, the open data on NFT transactions and predictions are mushrooming ever since 2021.

This research intends to examine the platforms for the current open data access on NFT works and analyse the potential social impacts on the understanding of NFT. The research follows the new materialism philosophy as the main guidance, applying the Actor-network Theory (ANT) to connect technology and social life (Latour, 2007). The aim is to combine the digital technical examination of NFT trading platforms and examine how the open data on the trading site has impacted the social aspect, which refers to the general users' experience and perceptions of NFT. The research will firstly conduct an overview explanation of the NFT concepts, open data definition, and the implication of social media open data on digital platforms, and how the transparent framework allows more data to be retrieved and tracked online to be accessed by the public. Furthermore, the research uses the Walkthrough method to thoroughly investigate the step-by-step process of the open data platform in NFT. It is the digital observation of the NFT user experience from registration, profile building, daily interactions, and any other changes of status (Light et al., 2018). The Walkthrough method is also suitable for social media platform examinations, in order to understand how specific functions and technical frameworks have an impact on the users' social life. To complement the observation data, I explore NFT from various

social perspectives, including how the open data has access to the encrypted information, how the data has been displayed, and how it effectively impacts the transaction of NFT. The conclusion is drawn on the potential social impacts on users' daily experience of the NFT applications and identifies the significance of open data access for NFT work, in terms of the NFT transaction. As NFT is a relatively underdeveloped research topic, this will be the first research on the interdisciplinary research of data science, NFT technologies, and social understandings. The research is aiming to provide references for further research on accessing open data through various digital platforms and its social impacts.

References

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